

Rational construction of porous cobalt nanoparticle integrated nitrogen doped hollow carbon nanostructures for peptide agonist exendin-4 biosensing

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we designed a point-of-care (POC) testing electrochemical biosensor using an integrated biosensing assay based on hollow-like nitrogen-doped carbon nanostructures combined with cobalt nanoparticles (Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs). These are functionalized with Anti-Exendin-4 Antibodies (Anti-Ex-4-Abs) and Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) to create sensitive probes (Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, and CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA) for the ultrasensitive detection of exendin-4 (Ex-4), a peptide agonist used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Among the cobalt-based carbon nanostructures, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA nanoprobe demonstrated superior ability to specifically recognize Ex-4. This was indicated by a significant decrease in the chronoamperometric (CA) i-t current response, facilitating low-level detection of Ex-4. The nanoprobe was capable of detecting Ex-4 concentrations ranging from 1.0 to 90.0 pM, with a sensitivity of 0.60 μA/pM and a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.46 pM (S/N = 3). Furthermore, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA nanoprobe demonstrated the ability to detect nanomolar levels of Ex-4 in blood serum and urine samples, achieving satisfactory recovery rates of 96–104%. The proposed electrostatic interaction chemistry approach establishes a remarkable platform for constructing a peptide agonist biosensor that is effective for detecting Ex-4 in real human serum and urine samples.

1. Introduction

Diabetes is a significant endocrine metabolic disorder and one of the foremost health challenges globally (Zimmet, 2017). It is primarily categorized into two forms: (i) type 1 diabetes, characterized by a deficiency of insulin, and (ii) type 2 diabetes, which involves insulin resistance. Both forms are directly associated with decreased secretion of peptides from the pancreatic islets (Campbell and Newgard, 2021). The role of glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) is crucial for blood glucose regulation, as it stimulates insulin secretion in a glucose-dependent manner following food intake. This process is considered a key

component of the "incretin effect" (Drucker and Holst, 2023). Notably, the endogenous GLP-1 signalling system significantly aids glucose homeostasis through various effects beyond just stimulating insulin secretion, and it has garnered considerable interest in diabetes treatment (Nauck et al., 2021). Although GLP1 has a very short half-life in the treatment cycle owing to rapid cleavage by the protease dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP4), alternate GLP1 is essential for the treatment of type-2 diabetes (Nauck et al., 2021). Exendin-4 (Ex-4), a natural agonist of the glucagon-like peptide-1-receptor (GLP1R) with a molecular weight of 4.20 kDa, was firstly isolated from the venom of the Gila monster (*Heloderma suspectum*), which is comprised of residues of 39

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amino acid residues (Zhong et al., 2018). Ex-4 mimics various biological actions of GLP1R on pancreatic islets, the cerebrospinal nervous system, and the digestive tract that mediate dietary intake and glucose homeostasis processes owing to its extended plasma half-life compared with GLP1R (Kim et al., 2011; Zhong et al., 2018). Moreover, Ex-4 has indeed been considered an efficient peptide agonist for minimizing blood glucose levels in type-2 diabetes mellitus patients (T2DM) (Smits and Holst, 2023). The U.S. Food and Drug Administration approved the synthetic form of Ex-4, called Exenatide, for the supplemental treatment of T2DM, which normalizes glucose metabolism and insulin secretion by amplifying glucose-dependent insulin secretion and preventing elevated postprandial glucagon production (Nauck et al., 2021). Due to the fluctuating nature of blood glucose levels and the narrow therapeutic range, it is important to develop a potential method that uses systematic screening of the blood concentrations of Ex-4 to attain reliable and efficient monitoring of T2DM patients. Thus, designing a nanostructured amperometric electrochemical biosensor for quantification of Ex-4 could have a direct impact on human health screening and diagnosis.

Efforts have been made to develop noble/non-noble metal nanoparticle (Co, Ni, Fe, Pt@Pd, Au NPs)-based sensing platforms with high sensitivity and selectivity owing to their superior characteristics of tunable nanostructures, high conductivity, large active surface area, high anticorrosion ability, and good biocompatibility (Chang et al., 2024; Jia et al., 2024; Kannan and John, 2011; Li et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024; Naderi and Shahrokhian, 2023; Tan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022, 2023, 2024; Zhang et al., 2020). It is important to mention here that carbon materials are considered potential supporting substrates because of their further enhancement of specific surface areas, faster electron transfer, and improved activity. Besides, nitrogen-doped carbon can offer numerous active sites towards various target molecules, as well as larger anchoring sites for metallic precursors through functional groups (-COOH and -NH₂), which in turn prevents agglomeration of the associated metal nanostructures and finally displays an enhanced analytical outcome (Li et al., 2020; Muthusankar et al., 2020). For instance, Li et al., fabricated Co NPs embedded on N-doped carbon nanotube arrays (Co NPs/NCNTs) for the electrochemical sensing of H₂O₂ with a low detection limit (LOD: 32.4 nM) and a higher sensitivity (568.47 μA mM⁻¹ cm⁻²), which is mainly attributed to the existence of larger Co NPs and atomic Co-Nx active sites in the NCNTs along with synergistic effects and improved N-content and conductivity of the electrocatalyst (Li et al., 2020). On the other side, Gopu et al., reported an N-CQD@Co₃O₄/MWCNTs-based nanocomposite toward the concurrent and sensitive detection of anticancer and antibiotic drugs (flutamide and nitrofurantoin) in human urine samples for the active screening of pharmacotherapy. The LOD of the developed sensor was about 16.9 and 44.0 nM, respectively, which is exclusively due to the 4H⁺/4e⁻ redox process on the surface of N-CQD@Co₃O₄/MWCNTs (Muthusankar et al., 2020). Inspired by previous reports, we developed a point-of-care (POC) electrochemical biosensor platform utilizing hollow nitrogen-doped carbon nanostructures combined with cobalt nanoparticles (Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs). We immobilized Anti-Exendin-4 antibodies (Anti-Ex-4-Abs) along with bovine serum albumin (BSA) to create sensitive probes (Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, and CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA) for the ultrasensitive detection of Ex-4, a peptide agonist used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Among the cobalt-based carbon nanostructures, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA nanoprobe demonstrated significant potential for specifically recognizing Ex-4. This capability was achieved by decreasing the chronoamperometric signals, enabling low-level detection down to 1.0 pM through electrostatic interaction chemistry approach.

2. Experimental section

Reagents, synthesis of various Co-based HNCNs nanostructures, instrumentations, and electrochemical preparation procedures are

provided in the supporting information.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of Co nanoparticles incorporated HNCNs samples

The stepwise synthesis of three various Co nanoparticles intercalated with nitrogen-doped carbon nanocages (Co-HNCNs) is shown in Scheme S1. The detailed SEM image results clearly depicted the initial transformation of ZIF-67 rhombic dodecahedral particles into hollow Co nanostructures (Fig. 1A and B). In particular, the unique smooth and flat-solid surfaces of the ZIF-67 structure were finely tuned into crumpled, furrowed, and bulbous-like nanostructures with a rough-coarse surface (Fig. 1C). In addition, the rough-coarse surface mainly originated from the formation of Co-nanoparticles, which were randomly distributed on both the inner and outer surfaces of the hollow ZIF-67 framework. Subsequently, the hollow Co@HNCNs nanostructures were further annealed in air at 500 °C and converted to hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs (Fig. 1D–F), which incorporated larger Co nanoparticles (*vide infra*). Finally, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample was further annealed at 700 °C in the presence of upstream nitrogen gas and NaH₂PO₂, which resulted in hollow-like agglomerated CoP@HNCNs nanostructures (Fig. 1G–I) that were comprised of agglomerated CoP nanoparticles. This result is clearly evidenced by the structural decomposition of ZIF-67 at a higher temperature, which induced shrinkage of the spherical morphology, followed by severe agglomeration of the produced Co nanoparticles. The Kirkendall effect, a typical metallurgy phenomenon, has recently developed as a unique self-templated approach for the synthesis of hollow nanocrystals with considerably high-yield and fine control over size and morphology (Hussain et al., 2022; Tianou et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2023). Notably, this mechanism is potentially used to obtain hollow nanocrystals of cobalt oxides and chalcogenides; extensive efforts have been made to promote the Kirkendall effect in constructing hollow nanostructures of various morphologies (i.e., spheres, nanotubes, and dendrites) and compositions (i.e., bimetallic alloys, non-metallic oxides, and ternary systems) (Du et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2022). Typically, Kirkendall voids form during the reaction of solid nanocrystals with species in their environments, where the preferred diffusion of atoms or ions from core material to the reaction interface leads to an unbalanced external material fluctuation and concurrent formation and coalescence of vacancies inside the nanocrystals. For instance, recent studies have discovered that ZIF-67 can release Co²⁺ ions in a water-containing system due to the coordination-dissociation equilibrium. When certain anions exist in the system, such as OH⁻ ions, released Co²⁺ ions will react with them to produce a precipitate on the surface of ZIF-67. Then, the exhaustion of Co²⁺ ions will break the coordination-dissociation equilibrium of ZIF-67, which results in the release of more Co²⁺ ions; thus, a precipitate is continuously produced (He et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2018). Finally, new products with hollow structures can be formed, and this overall process is called the Kirkendall effect. In our study, the addition of Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O (Mo ions) was intended to etch the ZIF-67 particles, thereby inducing voids/or cracks, i.e., the conversion of ZIF-67 into a hollow carbon structure through the Kirkendall effect. The etching time was carefully controlled to ensure that only the central portion of ZIF-67 was dissolved while preserving its external structure. Thus, it was verified that the optimal reaction temperature was ≈500 °C, at which the ZIF-67 network retained its original morphology and chemical stability (Lee et al., 2020; Torad et al., 2014). The EDS analysis confirmed that Co, N, C, O, and P elements were distributed throughout the composition of the respective samples (Fig. S2).

We then characterized the as-synthesized Co@HNCNs nanostructures using HR-TEM imaging analysis, and the results are shown in Fig. 2. As shown in Fig. 2A–D, Co nanoparticles with a size range of 5–11 nm were distributed throughout the Co@HNCNs nanocage framework to become an ideal integrated nanostructure. Further, the HR-TEM

Fig. 1. Low to high-resolution SEM images of Co@HNCNs (A–C), Co₃O₄@HNCNs (D–F), and CoP@HNCNs samples (G–I).

Fig. 2. Low to high resolution TEM images of hollow-like nanocages of Co@HNCNs (A–E), Co₃O₄@HNCNs (G–K), and CoP@HNCNs (M–Q), and corresponding SAED patterns (F, L, and R), respectively. The EELS mapping pictures of Co, P, O, C, and N elements from CoP@HNCNs nanostructures (bottom row).

image taken from the nanoparticle inside the yellow square (Fig. 2E) clearly revealed the distance between the lattice fringes d -facing was about 0.27 and 0.16 nm, which were mainly attributed to the (102) and (100) planes of Co nanocrystalline facets. The Co_3O_4 @HNCNs lattice fringe distances are 0.271, 0.203, and 0.163 nm at 78.96° and 122.41° , respectively, which correspond to the orthorhombic Co-phase, visualized through the [12-2] zone axis of the crystalline domain. To confirm this, a SAED pattern was recorded for the Co@HNCNs nanocage framework, which revealed the formation of pure crystalline lattices of Co nanoparticles (see Fig. 2F). On the other side, the TEM images of the Co_3O_4 @HNCNs sample are displayed in Fig. 2G-L. Careful inspection of these TEM images revealed that the size of the Co nanoparticles increased (8–14 nm) without any aggregation, and the porosity of the ZIF-67 sample was considerably improved (Fig. 2G-I). It is important to

mention that the annealing process plays a critical role in isolating the nanoparticles and improving the dispersibility of the Co nanoparticles (Fig. 2J). The HR-TEM image of Co_3O_4 @HNCNs exhibited a well-defined lattice fringe d -facing of 0.24 and 0.27 nm, which corresponded to the (311) and (220) crystallographic planes, respectively (Fig. 2K). The obtained results further indicated that the Co nanoparticles in the Co_3O_4 @HNCNs sample were completely entrapped within the carbon layers and formed hollow-like nanocages of Co_3O_4 @HNCNs, which is consistent with the SEM images. The SAED pattern of Co_3O_4 @HNCNs (Fig. 2L) further evidenced the presence of not only the (311) and (220) planes but also high-active indexed facets such as (400), (440), and (511), which play a vital role in catalytic or biosensing applications (Liu et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2019; Yuanfeng et al., 2020). The lattice fringe distances of Co_3O_4 @HNCNs were 0.277, 0.240,

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of hollow-like nanocages of Co@HNCNs (A), Co_3O_4 @HNCNs (B), and CoP@HNCNs (C) samples. The survey XPS of Co_3O_4 @HNCNs (D) and corresponding Co 2p (E), C 1s (F), N 1s (G), and O 1s (H) regions. The O 1s (I) and P 2p (J) regions were represented the Anti-Ex-4-Abs functionalized on the hollow-like Co_3O_4 @HNCNs and CoP@HNCNs samples, respectively.

and 0.132 nm at 60.80°, and 121.90°, respectively, which corresponded to the monoclinic Co-phase, visualized through the [11-3] zone axis of the crystalline domain. Lastly, the TEM images of CoP@HNCNs nanostructures exhibited bumpy hollow-like nanocages of ZIF-67 framework (Fig. 2M-O) surrounded by agglomerated or fused CoP nanoparticles with a size of 20–30 nm (Fig. 2P), which is obviously due to the high-temperature annealing treatment, and the obtained results were consistent with the SEM images. By comparing the overall TEM analysis, the Co nanoparticles were bulged and blocked the fine porous surface of the CoP@HNCNs nanostructures; thus, the annealing process played a significant role in the preparation of tunable and improved dispersibility of Co nanoparticles. Further, the HR-TEM image of bumpy hollow-like nanocages of CoP@HNCNs structures showed lattice fringes with *d*-spacings of 0.23 and 0.18 nm, which corresponded to the (201) and (211) planes of CoP nanoparticles (Fig. 2Q). The lattice fringe distances of CoP@HNCNs were 0.230, 0.184, and 0.109 nm at 58.40°, and 119.10°, respectively, which correspond to the cubic Co phase, visualized through the [11-3] zone axis of the crystalline domain. The SAED not only depicts the (201) and (211) planes but also other pure crystalline facets such as the (011), (101), (200), (204), and (301) planes (Fig. 2R). Finally, the EELS mapping of CoP@HNCNs nanostructures exhibited a uniform distribution of Co, P, O, C, and N elements, which is consistent with the EDS analysis (bottom row in Fig. 2).

The hollow-like nanocages of the Co@HNCNs sample displayed well-defined crystalline patterns of (002), (020), (100), (101), (102), (110), and (200), which correspond to ZIF-67 carbon (JCPDS No. 026–1076) and Co (JCPDS No. 030–0443), respectively (Fig. 3A)(Liu et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2020), evidencing the presence of nanosized Co particles within the ZIF-67 framework. Subsequently, the XRD pattern analysis of Co₃O₄@HNCNs was also carried out and displayed typical characteristic diffraction peaks of (002), (111), (220), (311), (400), (422), (511), and (440), which correspond to ZIF-67 carbon (JCPDS No. 026–1076) and Co (JCPDS No. 001–1152), respectively (Fig. 3B)(Deori et al., 2013). The predominant sharp peaks of the hollow-like nanocages of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample when compared to the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample were mainly attributed to the high-temperature (500 °C) calcination effect, and the Co particles were completely transformed into Co₃O₄-NPs on the ZIF-67 framework and confirmed the absence of other Co-phases during the XRD measurements. Finally, the XRD pattern of the CoP@HNCNs sample displayed several noticeable characteristic diffraction peaks of (002), (101), (011), (200), (111), (201), (112), (211), (103), (020), (301), and (204), which correspond to ZIF-67 carbon (JCPDS No. 026–1076) and CoP (JCPDS No. 024–0497), respectively (Fig. 3C)(Zhou et al., 2021). The survey XPS spectra of all the CoP@HNCNs samples (Fig. 3D: Co₃O₄@HNCNs; Fig. S3A: Co@HNCNs; and Fig. S3B: CoP@HNCNs) clearly reveal the existence of C, N, Co, P, and O elements. The high-resolution XPS spectrum of Co 2p of the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample exhibited six noticeable peaks at 777.8, 780.6, 784.5, 792.9, 796.8, and 802.3 eV. The peak identified at 777.8 eV was attributed to the Co³⁺ 2P_{3/2} peak within the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample, whereas the peak found at 780.6 eV corresponded to the Co²⁺ 2P_{3/2} peak. In addition, the third peak, located at 784.5 eV, was called the shake-up satellite peak for the as-synthesized Co-material(Xu et al., 2022). On the other hand, the higher energy peak placed at 792.9 eV was mainly related to Co³⁺, whereas the high-spin Co²⁺ 2P_{1/2} peak was observed at 796.8 eV and the corresponding shake-up satellite peak at 802.3 eV, which can be assigned to the satellite peak for the Co₃O₄ nanoparticles system (Fig. 3E). Notably, no feeble peak at 776.0 eV relates to the absence of Co residual metallic features, strongly implying that the high-temperature treatment process is very effective for synthesizing hollow-like nanocages of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample(Xu et al., 2022).

The C 1s XPS of the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample displayed three major peaks, that is, 282.9, 283.3, 284.1, and 285.2 eV, which were attributed to the C-C (Co-C), C=C, C-C, and C-N=O peaks from the ZIF-67 framework nanostructure, respectively(Xu et al., 2022).

Notably, the existence of a peak at approximately 282.9 eV was related to Co-C, signifying the presence of cobalt metal in the ZIF-67 framework structure and suggesting that the Co-nanoparticles were anchored on the hollow-like carbon nanocages via Co-C bonds (Fig. 3F). This metal-carbon linkage typically appears at the interfaces between the metal terminations and the carbon surface, which can prevent Co-metal leaching(Li et al., 2018). N 1s XPS displayed three peaks at 396.0, 397.5, 398.8, 400.6, and 404.7 eV, which were matched with the pyridinic-N, Co-N_x, pyrrolic-N, graphitic-N, and N-O_x peaks (Fig. 3G)(Liu et al., 2022). It is important to mention here that the presence of pyrrolic and pyridinic-N species played a critical role as anchor points for the integration of Co-nanoparticles, while graphitic-N was embedded into the carbon matrix, which facilitated the effective accommodation of more numbers of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the hollow-like nanocages of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample and offered efficient electrochemical detection performance. The O 1s XPS was fitted into four main components, located at 529.4, 530.5, 531.7, and 532.8 eV, which correspond to Co-O, Co-O-C, Co-OH, and C-O-C, respectively (Fig. 3H). The small peak centered at 532.8 eV was ascribed to the oxygen in the lattice from the hollow-like nanocages of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample. The elemental composition of the as-synthesized Co@HNCNs samples was derived from XPS (Fig. S3) and BET surface area (Fig. S4) analyses were provided in the supporting information.

3.2. Electrochemical characterizations of Co nanoparticles@HNCNs electrodes

The stepwise construction of the proposed Ex-4 biosensor electrode is depicted in Scheme S2. As shown in Fig. 4A, the bare GCE exhibited a semicircle profile with an R_{ct} value of 174.6 Ω, which depicts the interfacial electron-transfer rate of the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} probe between the solution and the electrode (Fig. 4A, curve a). Afterwards, the GEC surface was incorporated with rhombic dodecahedral ZIF-67 particles that are HNCNs, which exhibited a small decrease in the R_{ct} value of 162.9 Ω, indicating slightly improved electronic conductivity owing to its porous nature and the interconnected conducting N-doped carbon elements (Fig. 4, curve b). Notably, the modification of Co nanoparticles on the surface of HNCNs/GCE, that is, hollow-like nanocages of Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs samples, resulted in a noticeable decrease in R_{ct} values of 109.6Ω (Fig. 4A, curve c), 28.2Ω (Fig. 4A, curve d), and 72.9Ω (Fig. 4A, curve e), respectively. Among the Co nanoparticles, the hollow nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs exhibited the smallest R_{ct} value. This is mainly attributed to the presence of dispersed Co nanoparticles on the HNCNs interface, which enhances the overall conductivity of the catalyst. The high specific internal (78.7 m²/g) and external (73.9 m²/g) surface areas, along with the fairly uniform distribution of Co nanoparticles into the hollow network-like nanostructure, not only provide a large number of mesopores but also generate more active sites. This allows for faster diffusion of the electrolyte to access available reaction sites (Co²⁺/Co³⁺ vs. [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox probe), facilitating effective interaction between the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox probe and the surfaces as well as the mesopores of Co₃O₄@HNCNs. Consequently, this results in enhanced conductivity and lower EIS signals. Furthermore, the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs comprised various metallic valence states (Co²⁺/Co³⁺) and the formation of highly ordered N-doped porous carbon, which enormously enhanced electron transfer at the interface of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs modified electrode and the electrolyte solution ([Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox probe)(Peng et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2018). Next, the immobilization of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the surface of hollow-like nanocages of Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs samples was further characterized by EIS measurements. As shown in Fig. 4B, Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (Fig. 4B, curve a), CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (Fig. 4B, curve b), and Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (Fig. 4B, curve c) exhibited R_{ct} values of 614.3, 840.1, and 956.7Ω, respectively, indicating the successful immobilization of

Fig. 4. (A) EIS of bare GCE (curve a), HNCNs (curve b), Co@HNCNs (curve c), Co₃O₄@HNCNs (curve d), and CoP@HNCNs (curve e) electrodes scanned from 0.1 Hz to 1 kHz in 0.1 M PBS + 1 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} solution. (B) EIS of Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (curve a), CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (curve b), and Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs (curve c), Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (curve d), CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (curve e), and Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (curve f) electrodes scanned from 0.1 Hz to 1 kHz in 0.1 M PBS + 1 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} solution. (C) Bar graphs obtained using real impedance (*Z'* Ohm) value of various Co based HNCNs nanomaterials modified electrodes. (D) CA profiles of Co₃O₄@HNCNs electrode scanned against various applied potentials: 0.7 V (curve a), 0.8 V (curve b), 0.9 V (curve c), 1.0 V (curve d), and 1.1 V (curve e) in 0.1 M PBS + 1 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} solution, and (E) corresponding *i-t* current profile graph. (F) CA *i-t* current profiles of Co@HNCNs (curve a), Co₃O₄@HNCNs (curve b), and CoP@HNCNs (curve c) electrodes in 0.1 M PBS + 1 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} solution at an applied potential of 1.0 V, and (G) corresponding replica analysis plot.

Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the surface of hollow-like nanocages of all Co nanostructures. The notable difference between the isoelectric points (IEP) of Co-materials (Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs) (≥ 8.40) and exendin-4 antibodies (~ 4.60) enabled an ideal environment for the successful incorporation of exendin-4 antibodies via electrostatic interactions (ester-like bridging) (Kittaka and Morimoto, 1980; Parks, 1965; Tomono et al., 2020; Wolff et al., 2021) and formed the immunocomplex, which strongly hindered transfer of the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox probe, preventing the admission of the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox species to the Co₃O₄@HNCNs electrode surface, resulting in an increasing *R*_{ct} value (Kang et al., 2020). Among Co materials, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs exhibited a higher *R*_{ct} value, which is mainly attributed to the following reasons: (i) the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs comprise not only a larger active surface area but also their porous nature, which can assess the superior amount of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on their surface. (ii) the fairly uniform distribution of Co₃O₄ nanoparticles into the inherited cavities as well as on the surface significantly enables the immobilization of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the interior and onto the surface of the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs via π - π stacking interactions (between polypeptide chains from Anti-Ex-4-Abs and nitrogen doped hollow carbon nanostructures from Co₃O₄@HNCNs) and van der Waals' forces (Kang et al., 2020). (iii) the internal and external surface areas of Co₃O₄@HNCNs nanostructures

were calculated as 78.7 and 73.9 m² g⁻¹, respectively (Fig. S4), which is higher than the internal and external surface areas of Co@HNCNs (43.4 and 36.8 m² g⁻¹) and CoP@HNCNs samples 18.1 and 14.7 m² g⁻¹) also play an important role in immobilization of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the surface of Co₃O₄@HNCNs modified electrode. It is important to mention here that the low surface-active area (see above) and random distribution of few Co nanoparticles from Co@HNCNs (Fig. 4B, curve a); while the aggregated CoP nanoparticles on the surface of CoP@HNCNs (Fig. 4B, curve b) did not provide an ideal environment for accessing a larger amount of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on their surface, which resulted in a small increase in *R*_{ct} values. The introduction of BSA to block the non-specific binding sites of Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (Fig. 4B, curve d), CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (Fig. 4B, curve e), and Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA (Fig. 4B, curve f) and resulted in further improvement in EIS responses of 1045.3, 1254.1, and 1620.9 Ω , respectively, for the above electrodes, which is obviously due to complete blocking of electron transfer path between the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox probe and modified electrodes indicating the successful fabrication of the Ex-4 biosensor electrode (Laochai et al., 2022). The bar plot (Fig. 4C) shows the obtained EIS responses against the stepwise construction of various Co nanoparticle-based Ex-4 biosensing electrodes, which demonstrates that the fabrication and modification steps were effective.

The XPS spectra of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs interface

exhibited a considerable increase in the intensity of the O 1s peak because of the immobilization of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on Co₃O₄@HNCNs. The O1s of Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs interface fitted into five components, which were located at 528.7, 529.4, 530.2, 531.0, and 532.6 eV, corresponding to the Co-O, Co-O-C, Co-OH, C-O-C, and O_{ads} (Fig. 3I). The Co-O peak shifted to a lower binding energy (0.7 eV) when compared to the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample, and the intensity increased after immobilizing Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the Co₃O₄@HNCNs interface owing to the improved oxygen contents (Fig. 3J). (Wahab et al., 2009) Moreover, an additional peak at 532.6 eV was corresponding to the adsorbed oxygen moiety from the carboxylic functionalities of the Anti-Ex-4-Abs. On the other side, the P 2p-region of the Anti-Ex-4-Abs immobilized on hollow-like aggregated nanocages of the CoP@HNCNs sample displayed well-defined distinctive peaks at 129.8 and 130.6 eV, which were ascribed to the adsorbed P-elements (P 2p_{3/2} and P 2p_{1/2}) from the CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs sample. The higher binding energy peaks at 133.1 and 134.1 eV were related to P-O and adsorbed oxygen species (Fig. 3J) from the Anti-Ex-4-Abs (Khalid et al., 2018). We further verified the formation of immunocomplex (via electrostatic interaction), i.e., the Anti-Ex-4-Abs functionalization on the hollow-like nanocages of Co₃O₄@HNCNs using FT-IR spectroscopy (see Fig. S5 and corresponding descriptions in the supporting information).

The sensitive and selective detection of Ex-4 was performed using both HNCNs and Co nanoparticles integrated with HNCNs nanomaterials through the CA method. Prior to Ex-4 detection, the ideal experimental parameters were optimized; thus, the steady-state current response behaviour of all the electrodes was measured in a 0.1 M PBS solution. The chronoamperometry (i-t) responses inherently measured the optimized stable steady-state response current over time (50 s) to attain better electrochemical performance. Based on the results from Fig. 4A and B, we chose the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs electrode for investigating the influence of the Ex-4 detection potential from 0.7 to 1.1 V at a constantly stirred 0.1 M PBS solution. As can be seen from Fig. 4D, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4 Ab/BSA electrode was examined for i-t current response by applying 0.7 V and observed that 0.50 μA (Fig. 4D, curve a), which is mainly due to the generation of background noise that affects the i-t response current; thereafter, while increasing the applied potential up to 1.0 V (Fig. 4D, curves b-d), the i-t current response was gradually increased up to 29.7 μA because of accelerating the activity of the fabricated biosensing Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA interface. Notably, the i-t current response was considerably decreased (18.63 μA) while applying 1.10 V (Fig. 4D, curve e), which was mainly attributed to the destabilization of the constructed biosensor interface (Fu et al., 2015). The corresponding i-t current response plot clearly revealed that 1.0 V was ideal for further Ex-4 biosensing experiments (Fig. 4E). Next, we studied the CA i-t current responses of Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, and CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA in a 0.1 M constantly stirred PBS solution. The Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode (Fig. 4F, curve a) displayed a steady state i-t current response of 23.2 μA; at the same time, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode (Fig. 4F, curve b) displayed an enhanced i-t current response of 29.7 μA. Finally, the CoP@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode (Fig. 4F, curve c) displayed a decreased i-t current response of 26.6 μA due to the aggregated nature of the CoP nanoparticles, which diminished the number of active sites and prevented effective ion transport. Despite the incorporation of a larger amount of Anti-Ex-4-Abs on the surface of Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA, it still displayed enhanced i-t current responses when compared to the other Co@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrodes. Based on the summary (Fig. 4G) of the above results, we chose the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode for the ultralow-level detection of Ex-4 in real samples. We have studied the influence of Anti-Ex-4-Abs loading (Fig. S6) and immobilization time for the detection of Ex-4 biosensor. Notably, the amount of antibody loading and incubation time are indeed considered crucial factors in influencing the specific binding efficacy against Ex-4 molecules, which directly play

vital roles in the detection performance of Ex-4 biosensors. As shown in Fig. S6, the Anti-Ex-4-Abs loading on the Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs samples was spectrophotometrically analyzed, and the corresponding loading analysis is displayed in Fig. S6. Among the Co-based nanostructures, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs sample exhibited the highest loading on its surface when compared to the other samples (Co@HNCNs and CoP@HNCNs), indicating that the 10 μg/mL was optimal for the enhanced detection of Ex-4. Further, we have also studied the influence of Anti-Ex-4-Abs immobilization time for the detection of Ex-4 biosensor. As shown in Fig. S7A, the Ex-4 detection performance gradually increased up to 30 min of the Anti-Ex-4-Abs immobilization time, and afterwards the Ex-4 detection response decreased; the corresponding Ex-4 detection response current plot was displayed in Fig. S7B, implying that the 30 min incubation time was an optimal period for the Anti-Ex-4-Abs functionalization time for Ex-4 detection, which offered an enhanced detection output with faster responses.

3.3. Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA-based biosensing of Ex-4

The trace level of Ex-4 was comprehensively assessed by the difference in the i-t current response ($\Delta i-t$), i.e., $\Delta i-t_{\text{current}} = i-t_{\text{current}}(\text{before the addition of Ex-4}) - i-t_{\text{current}}(\text{after the addition of Ex-4})$ was calculated with respect to the amount of Ex-4 added into the PBS solution or real samples such as blood serum and urine. As can be seen from Fig. 5A, curve a illustrates the i-t current response obtained for the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA biosensing electrode at an applied potential of 1.0 V. Notably, introducing 1 pM of Ex-4 into the constantly stirred 0.1 M PBS solution indicated a clear drop in the CA i-t current response, which certainly evidenced the specific capture of peptide agonist Ex-4 by the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA biosensing electrode. Afterwards, the continued addition of various concentrations of Ex-4 (1, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 70, 80, and 90 pM) resulted in a steady and constant decrease in CA i-t current profiles, which indeed demonstrated the potential usefulness of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode towards the highly specific detection of Ex-4 (Fig. 5A, curves b-r). Various concentrations of Ex-4 ranging from 1 to 90 pM in 0.1 M PBS (pH = 7.2) were detected at a CA i-t curve response time interval of 50 s, and the corresponding calibration curve was plotted using difference in i-t current responses (Δi_{i-t}) with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.981 (Fig. 5B). The Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode used for the sensitive detection of Ex-4 was mainly attributed to some important properties, which include: (i) the hollow-like nanocages of ZIF-67 provide a larger porous surface, allowing for the attachment of more Co₃O₄ nanoparticles, which in turn attract more Anti-Ex-4-Abs to their surface via electrostatic interactions, i.e., a notable difference between the isoelectric points (IEP) of Co-based nanostructures (~8.40) and Anti-Ex-4-Abs (~4.60) enabled an ideal environment for the successful incorporation of Anti-Ex-4-Abs (ester-like bridging) (Madhu et al., 2020; Sekar et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). (ii) $\pi-\pi$ stacking interaction between polypeptide chains of Anti-Ex-4-Abs and nitrogen-doped hollow carbon nanostructures from Co₃O₄@HNCNs; (iii) the Co@HNCNs (Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs) nanohybrid not only inherited the cavities/voids and porous structures from the parent ZIF-67 but also features of the mesoporous carbon, which can enhance the adsorption ability of the Anti-Ex-4-Abs via van der Waals' force, heavy- and light chains from Anti-Ex-4-Abs and Co₃O₄@HNCNs nanostructures (Dalkas et al., 2014; Lucas et al., 2016; Mercante et al., 2021). The sensitivity of the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode toward the detection of Ex-4 was calculated as 0.60 μA μM/pM (n = 3) and the lowest LOD of 0.46 pM at a signal-to-noise ratio of 3S_b/m (S/N = 3), in which "S_b" is defined as the standard deviation of the signal in a blank solution (n = 5), while the sensitivity is the slope of the linear calibration plot. These notable features from the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode offer improved detection of Ex-4 through its unique and specific

Fig. 5. (A) CA i-t current responses obtained for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA}$ electrode in 0.1 M PBS solution (curve a), and stepwise addition of Ex-4: (curves b-r: 1, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 70, 80, and 90 pM) and (B) corresponding linear regression plot. (C) CA i-t current responses obtained for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA}$ electrode in 0.1 M PBS solution (curve a), followed by the addition of interferents such as creatinine (curve b; 1.0 nM), tryptophan (curve c; 10 nM), glycine (curve d; 10 nM), alanine (curve e; 10 nM), valine (curve f; 10 nM), uric acid (curve g; 1.0 nM), glucose (curve h; 1.0 nM), BSA + insulin (curve i; 0.5 nM), and Ex-4 (curve j; 50.0 pM), and (D) corresponding i-t current response bar-plot chart. (E) The CA i-t curve responses obtained on $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA}$ electrode alone (curve a), and in presence of different concentrations of Ex-4, i.e., 1.0 nM (curve b), 5.0 nM (curve c), 10.0 nM (curve d), 15.0 nM (curve e), 20.0 nM (curve f), and 25.0 nM (curve f) in PBS solution (pH = 7.20) containing blood serum sample, and (F) corresponding linear regression plot. (G) The CA i-t curve responses obtained on $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA}$ electrode alone (curve a), and in presence of different concentrations of Ex-4, i.e., 1.0 nM (curve b), 5.0 nM (curve c), 10.0 nM (curve d), 15.0 nM (curve e), 20.0 nM (curve f), and 25.0 nM (curve f) in PBS solution (pH = 7.20) containing urine sample, and (H) corresponding linear regression plot.

recognition with excellent sensitivity and selectivity, faster detection response time, extensive linear detection range, and comparatively lower detection limit (0.46 pM). It is worthwhile to mention here that the LOD of the as-fabricated Ex-4 biosensor is considerably comparable with the recently reported literature (Table S1). Thus, to examine the binding affinity (specificity) of the biosensing probe electrode, the K_d between the Anti-Ex-4-Abs and Ex-4 was calculated using a least-squares fit of the $C_{\text{Ex-4}} \text{ vs. } C_{\text{Ex-4}}/\Delta I_{i-t}$ result (Fig. S8) to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm model as follows (Eq. i):

$$\frac{C_{\text{Ex-4}}}{\Delta I_{i-t}} = \frac{1}{\Delta I_{i-t}^{\text{max}}} \cdot C_{\text{Ex-4}} + \frac{1}{\Delta I_{i-t}^{\text{max}}} \cdot K_d \quad (\text{i})$$

where $C_{\text{Ex-4}}$ is the concentration of Ex-4 in the PBS solution or real samples, ΔI_{i-t} is the Ex-4 biosensing responses, and $\Delta I_{i-t}^{\text{max}}$ is defined as the maximum response at higher $C_{\text{Ex-4}}$. From Eq. (i), the dissociation constants of Anti-Ex-4-Abs and Ex-4 were determined to be $K_d = \sim 1.20$ pM) in PBS, which is comparable to the LOD value indicating a higher binding affinity (Luzi et al., 2003) between the Anti-Ex-4-Abs bio-receptor and Ex-4. This confirmed the potential usefulness of the

designed biosensor for the detection of Ex-4. To assess the specificity of this Ex-4 biosensor, numerous interferent biomolecules present in practical real samples, including creatinine, insulin, glucose, uric acid, and some amino acids, were measured using the $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA}$ electrode. Biosensor selectivity was studied by assessing the influence of various relevant biomolecules, which are noticeably associated with actual blood serum or urine samples. (Kannan and John, 2011; Kannan et al., 2010) The interferent-free (Fig. 5C, curve a) and interfering biomolecules include creatinine (Fig. 5C, curve b; 1.0 nM), tryptophan (Fig. 5C, curve c; 10 nM), glycine (Fig. 5C, curve d; 10 nM), alanine (Fig. 5C, curve e; 10 nM), valine (Fig. 5C, curve f; 10 nM), uric acid (Fig. 5C, curve g; 1.0 nM), and glucose (Fig. 5C, curve h; 1.0 nM) resulted in negligible i-t current responses. In addition to the above, the interference analysis was also carried out by mixing the insulin with BSA in an equal ratio (1:1) in 0.1M PBS (Fig. 5C, curve i; 0.5 nM), indicating that the developed biosensor is highly selective toward the detection of Ex-4 with the cocktail interference mixture under the physiological environment. Concurrently, the addition of Ex-4 (Fig. 5C, curve j; 50.0 pM) into the same constantly stirred PBS solution resulted in a noticeable CA current drop, indicating the potential selectivity of the designed

Ex-4 biosensor. The selected concentrations of all the interference biomolecules were noticeably higher than the Ex-4. As shown in Fig. 5D, the bar plot derived from the respective *i-t* current responses of the Ex-4 biosensor against various interfering compounds was considerably lower (i.e., 3 to 4-fold less) than that of Ex-4. The obtained result clearly confirmed that there was no significant interference influence of the immobilized Anti-Ex-4-Abs along with BSA (because even non-specific interaction or physical adsorption was effectively prevented, as shown in Scheme S2, Route II) against interference analytes. In other words, it is worth mentioning that the different signal responses of the interfering biomolecules showed a slight change during the Ex-4 detection analysis. Although the concentrations of these interferences were 20–200 times higher than that of Ex-4, the CA *i-t* current response was only observed in the presence of 50 pM Ex-4. Therefore, the designed biosensor platform offers a higher selectivity for the determination of Ex-4.

3.4. Detection of Ex-4 in real samples using Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode

To assess the practicality and clinical relevance of the proposed biosensor, we detected the peptide agonist Ex-4 in human serum and urine samples; a 1:1 ratio of human serum or urine samples and 0.1 M PBS (pH = 7.2) was selected for the real-time detection analysis. The use of a 1:1 ratio (real sample to PBS solution) not only reduced the biological matrix effect but also enhanced the sensitivity and reproducibility of the developed biosensor platform. As shown in Fig. 5E, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode was examined in the absence (curve a) and presence of various concentrations of Ex-4 (curves b - g: 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 nM) injected into 0.1 M PBS (pH = 7.2) containing human serum samples. It is obvious that each step of Ex-4 addition resulted in a gradual decrease in CA *i-t* current responses, and the corresponding calibration plot with an R² value of 0.995 (Fig. 5F) ensures the dynamic Ex-4 detection response, which indicates that the proposed Ex-4 biosensing platform is potentially used for clinical testing analysis. We also detected the peptide agonist Ex-4 in human urine samples. As shown in Fig. 5G, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode was examined in the absence (curve a) and presence of various concentrations of Ex-4 (curves b - g: 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 nM) injected into 0.1 M PBS (pH = 7.2) containing human urine samples. It is obviously clear that each step of Ex-4 addition resulted in a gradual decrease in CA *i-t* current responses, and the corresponding calibration plot with a R² value of 0.986 (Fig. 5H) revealed the linear dynamic Ex-4 detection response, indicating that the proposed Ex-4 biosensing platform is potentially useful for clinical testing analysis in real-time analysis. The detection summary of Ex-4 in both real samples is displayed in Table S2 (blood serum sample) and Table S3 (urine sample), which confirmed the good recovery (Eq. ii) during the analysis (96–104%).

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = \frac{[\text{Spiked}]_{\text{Ex-4}} - [\text{Blank}]_{\text{Ex-4}}}{[\text{Standard solution}]_{\text{Ex-4}}} \quad (\text{ii})$$

Overall, the obtained results show that the designed biosensor platform can detect the agonist peptide Ex-4 in complexed biological samples and drive toward its potential clinical applications. The repeatability, reproducibility, and stability of Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA electrode were described in the supporting information (see Figs. S9, S10, and S11).

4. Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrated the synthesis and characterization of Co@HNCNs, Co₃O₄@HNCNs, and CoP@HNCNs nanostructures through a simple annealing process. We then developed a highly sensitive electrochemical biosensor for detecting the peptide agonist Ex-4. This biosensor, which incorporates Anti-Ex-4-Abs onto the surface of a porous Co-based HNCNs substrate, is designed for the efficient detection

of Ex-4, a key biomarker for the treatment of T2DM. Among the Co materials, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA nanoprobe effectively exhibited the specific capture of target Ex-4 by decreasing the CA *i-t* curve responses to progress the low-level sensitive detection via the formation of an immunocomplex. The CA *i-t* curves exhibited impressive analytical outcomes, showing a wide dynamic detection range for Ex-4 from 1.0 to 90.0 pM, with a sensitivity of 0.60 μA/pM and the LOD of 0.46 pM (S/N = 3). Moreover, the Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA nanoprobe demonstrated the potential to detect nanomolar levels of Ex-4 (1–25 nM) in blood serum and urine samples, achieving satisfactory recovery rates of 96–104%. The developed Co₃O₄@HNCNs/Anti-Ex-4-Abs/BSA-based electrochemical biosensing platform has demonstrated promising potential for detecting biomarkers and facilitating the early diagnosis of various critical diseases.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dr. Wei Zhang: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Ms. Bharathi Natarajan: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Dr. Palanisamy Kannan: Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization, Dr. Rostislav Medlín: Resources, Formal analysis, Data curation, Dr. Laurent Christophe Nicolai: Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Dr. Michal Procházka: Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Prof. Jan Minar: Formal analysis, Funding Acquisition, Dr. Palaniappan Subramanian: Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2024.116938>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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